

AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
DEVELOPMENT OF AN ANDROID APPLICATION FOR RECOGNIZING
HANDWRITING TEXT ON MOBILE DEVICES
BY
KAMAL ACHARYA
(Tribhuvan University)

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ABSTRACT

In today's world advancement in sophisticated scientific techniques is pushing further the limits of human outreach in various fields of technology. One such field is the field of character recognition commonly known as OCR (Optical Character Recognition).

In this fast paced world there is an immense urge for the digitalization of printed documents and documentation of information directly in digital form. And there is still some gap in this area even today. OCR techniques and their continuous improvisation from time to time is trying to fill this gap. This project is about devising an algorithm for recognition of hand written characters also known as HCR (Handwritten Character Recognition) leaving aside types of OCR that deals with recognition of computer or typewriter printed characters.

A novel technique is proposed for recognition English language characters using Artificial Neural Network including the schemes of feature extraction of the characters and implemented. The persistency in recognition of characters by the AN network was found to be more than 90% of times.

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

This project, 'Handwritten Character Recognition' is a software algorithm project to recognize any handwritten text efficiently on android devices with image as an input which can either be a previously stored image from the gallery or provided through camera.

Character recognition, usually abbreviated to optical character recognition or shortened OCR, is the mechanical or electronic translation of images of handwritten, typewritten or printed text (usually captured by a scanner) into NM machine-editable text. It is a field of research in pattern recognition, artificial intelligence and machine vision. Though academic research in the field continues, the focus on character recognition has shifted to implementation of proven techniques. Optical character recognition is a scheme which enables a computer to learn, understand, improvise and interpret the written or printed character in their own language, but present correspondingly as specified by the user. Optical Character Recognition uses the image processing technique to identify any character computer/typewriter printed or hand written. A lot of work has been done in this field. But a continuous improvisation of OCR techniques is being done based on the fact that algorithm must have higher accuracy of recognition, higher persistency in number of times of correct prediction and increased execution time.

The idea is to device efficient algorithms which get input in digital image format. After that it processes the image for better comparison. Then after the processed image is compared with already available set of font images. The last step gives a prediction of the character in percentage accuracy.

1.1 OBJECTIVE OF THE PROJECT

The objective of this project is to identify handwritten characters with the use of neural networks. We have to construct suitable neural network and train it properly. The program should be able to extract the characters one by one and map the target output for training purpose. After automatic processing of the image, the training dataset has to be used to train “classification engine” for recognition purpose. The program code has to be written in JAVA and supported with the usage of Graphical User Interface (GUI) using android.

Another objective of this project is to translate language, so this application can also be used as a language translator.

1.2 APPROACH

To solve the defined handwritten character recognition problem of classification we used android user interface and python as a backend with Neural Network Toolbox and Image Processing. The computation code is divided into the next categories:

- Pre-processing of the image
- Feature extraction
- Creating an Artificial Neural Network
- Training & Testing of the network
- Recognition
- Language translator

CHAPTER 2

TOOLS AND TECHNOLOGIES USED

2.1 ANDROID STUDIO (For user interface)

Android Studio is the official integrated development environment (IDE) for Google's Android operating system, built on JetBrains' IntelliJ IDEA software and designed specifically for Android development. It is available for download on Windows, macOS and Linux based operating systems. It is a replacement for the Eclipse Android Development Tools (ADT) as the primary IDE for native Android application development.

Features

The following features are provided in the current stable version:-

- Gradle-based build support
- Android-specific refactoring and quick fixes
- Lint tools to catch performance, usability, version compatibility and other problems
- Pro Guard integration and app-signing capabilities
- Template-based wizards to create common Android designs and components
- A rich layout editor that allows users to drag-and-drop UI components, option to preview layouts on multiple screen configurations.
- Support for building Android Wear apps

Built-in support for Google Cloud Platform, enabling integration with Firebase Cloud Messaging (Earlier 'Google Cloud Messaging') and Google App Engine.

Android Virtual Device (Emulator) to run and debug apps in the Android studio.

Android Studio supports all the same programming languages of IntelliJ (and C Lion) e.g. Java, C++, and more with extensions, such as Go; and Android Studio 3.0 or later

supports Kotlin and "Java 7 language features and a subset of Java 8 language features that vary by platform version."

2.2 FLASK (For interface between user interface and backend)

Flask is a micro web framework written in Python. It is classified as a microframework because it does not require particular tools or libraries. It has no database abstraction layer, form validation, or any other components where pre-existing third-party libraries provide common functions. However, Flask supports extensions that can add application features as if they were implemented in Flask itself. Extensions exist for object-relational mappers, form validation, upload handling, various open authentication technologies and several common framework related tools. Extensions are updated far more regularly than the core Flask program.

Applications that use the Flask framework include Pinterest, LinkedIn, and the community web page for Flask itself.

2.3 PYTHON

Python is an interpreted, high-level, general-purpose programming language. Created by Guido van Rossum and first released in 1991, Python has a design philosophy that emphasizes code readability, notably using significant whitespace. It provides constructs that enable clear programming on both small and large scales. Van Rossum led the language community until July 2018.

Python is dynamically typed and garbage-collected. It supports multiple programming paradigms, including procedural, object-oriented, and functional programming. Python features a comprehensive standard library, and is referred to as "batteries included".

Python interpreters are available for many operating systems. C Python, the reference implementation of Python, is open-source software and has a community-based development model. Python and C Python are managed by the non-profit Python Software Foundation.

CHAPTER 3

ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK

3.1 INTRODUCTION

An early phase of Neural Network was developed by Warren McCulloch and Walter Pitts in 1943 which was a computational model based on Mathematics and algorithm. This model paved the way for research which was focused on the application of Neural Networks in Artificial Intelligence.

Artificial neural network is basically a mesh of large number of interconnected cells. The arrangement of cells are such that each cell receives an input and drives an output for subsequent cells. Each cell has a pre-defined

The diagram below is a block diagram that depicts the structure and work flow of a created **Artificial Neural Network**. The neurons are interconnected with each other in a serial manner. The network consist of a number of hidden layers depending upon the resolution of comparison of inputs with the dataset.

Fig 3.1: Artificial Neural Network

3.2 CREATING AND TRAINING OF NETWORK

In case of character recognition we have to create a 2D vector of character images which can be fed to the network as ideal set of input variables. In our case there is a total of 26 capital English letters which we are to recognize.

Below is a set of characters written in binary form of 7x5 sized matrix of 26 capital English letters:

0	0	1	0	0
0	1	0	1	0
0	1	0	1	0
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Fig 3.2: Equivalent matrices of English alphabets

CHAPTER 4

IMAGE PROCESSING INVOLVED IN CHARACTER RECOGNITION

4.1 PRE-PROCESSING OF SAMPLE IMAGE

Pre-processing of the sample image involves few steps that are mentioned as follows:

Grey-scaling of RGB image

Grey-scaling of an image is a process by which an RGB image is converted into a black and white image. This process is important for Binarization as after grey-scaling of the image, only shades of grey remains in the image, binarization of such image is efficient

Binarization

Binarization of an image converts it into an image which only have pure black and pure white pixel values in it. Basically during binarization of a grey-scale image, pixels with intensity lower than half of the full intensity value gets a zero value converting them into black ones. And the remaining pixels get a full intensity value converting it into white pixels.

Inversion

Inversion is a process in which each pixel of the image gets a colour which is the inverted colour of the previous one. This process is the most important one because any character on a sample image can only be extracted efficiently if it contains only one colour which is distinct from the background colour. Note that it is only required if the objects we have to identify if of darker intensity on a lighter background.

The flow chart shown below illustrates the physical meaning of the processes that are mentioned above:

RGB => Grey-scaling => Binarization => Inversion
--

4.2 FEATURE EXTRACTION

Features of a character depicts the morphological and spatial characteristics in the image. Feature extraction is a method of extracting of features of characters from the sample image. There are basically two types of feature extraction:

- Statistical feature extraction
- Structural feature extraction

Statistical feature extraction

In this type of extraction the extracted feature vector is the combination of all the features extracted from each character. The associated feature in feature vector of this type of extraction is due to the relative positions of features in character image matrix.

Structural feature extraction

This is a primitive method of feature extraction which extracts morphological features of a character from image matrix. It takes into account the edges, curvature, regions, etc. This method extracts the features of the way character are written on image matrix.

The different methods used for feature extraction are

- Piecewise –linear regression
- Curve-fitting
- Zoning
- Chain code, etc.

The functions that are used in feature extraction are:

Indexing and labelling

This is a process by which distinct characters in an image are indexed and labelled in an image. Thus helps in classification of characters in image and makes feature extraction of characters simple.

Boxing and Cropping

This is a process of creating a boundary around the characters identified in an image. This helps by making cropping of characters easier. After boxing the characters are cropped out for storing them as input variables for recognition.

Reshaping and Resizing

Reshaping is done to change the dimensions of the acquired character in desired shape.

Resizing is done to reduce the size of characters to a particular minimum level.

CHAPTER 5

SIMULATION AND RESULTS

5.1 SIMULATION

5.1.1 Pre-processing of the image

First of all the image on which the characters are written by hand is required. Below is the example of one case in which an image sample is taken.

Fig 5.1: Original handwritten image sample

Fig 5.2: Binarization of the image

Fig 5.3: Inversion of binary image

5.1.2 Feature Extraction of characters from image

Indexing and Boxing of characters

Fig 5.4: Labelling and boxing of differentiated characters

Cropping, Reshaping and Resizing

Differentiation of characters is done by cropping the boxed characters of the pre-processed image. At first the sub-images are are cropped label by label in the sample image, then the character image array is resized to form a 7X5 matrix pixelated image. This is done because an image array can only be defined with all images of fixed size.

Also the size of the character image should be maintained to a size of 7X5 because the ideal character set is defined as a set of images with 7X5 sized 2D matrix with binary values.

For this to be achieved first the images are reshaped to a 7 by 5 aspect ratio image then resized into a 7 by 5 size image

Fig 5.5: Acquired character from the sample image

Fig 5.6: Image after resizing into a 7X5 sized image

5.1.3 Creating an Artificial Neural Network

The input is fed through the network which traverses through each neuron as it compares the input image with each neuron and gives the value in terms of a percentage of similarity between the input image and the neurons.

The neuron with having highest percentage of similarity to the input image is considered or estimated as the most favorable output which is most likely to that input.

In our case a network with 26 neurons and one hidden layer is enough.

Fig 5.7: Block diagram of an Artificial Neural Network

5.1.4 Training and testing the network

It is important to note that the network would not be immune to noisy hand written input if it is not trained properly. Or in other words, if the network is not trained with noisy set of characters along with the ideal set of characters, the network will not show the correct output every time. In fact all the handwritten characters remain irregular. So to make the network identify irregular shaped characters properly we must have to train the network with a noisy set of characters. In this case a set of noisy characters is obtained by adding some noise programmatically with some non-zero value of mean and variance.

Fig 5.8: A character from ideal set

Fig 5.9: Programmatically adding some noise to the character

5.2 RESULTS

5.2.1 Identification of characters

After proper training and testing of the network, the pixelated 7 by 5 sized image of 'A' is fed to the network as input. Then the out we get is the resultant 2D matrix plot same as the character 'A' from the ideal dataset which was fed to the network as training dataset.

Fig 5.10: The character 'A' identified by network

CHAPTER 6

MODULES OF PROJECT

Basically our project has been divided into five modules which are as follows:

Fig.6.1 Modules

6.1. ADAPTIVE THRESHOLDING

- Firstly the optimal threshold for binarization is computed by using the Otsu method.
- Threshold is calculated to separate the handwriting from the background.
- With this threshold, the image is converted to black and white, thus highlighting the handwritten characters which it contains.

6.2 DILATION

- The value of the output pixel is the maximum value of all pixels in the neighborhood. In a binary image, a pixel is set to 1 if any of the neighboring pixels have the value 1.
- Morphological dilation makes objects more visible and fills in small holes in objects.

6.3. SEGMENTATION

- The next step is to segment the areas corresponding to the letters of the handwritten words from the image converted to black and white.
- For this we scan the image from left to right and from bottom to top, and finding a black pixel, will consider it as the original area delimiting the character from which is part of.
- This area is further expanded in three directions, namely top, left and right, so as to include the rest of the pixels that are part of the handwritten character.
- Save the new area
- Convert the new area into a matrix of 0 and 1.

6.4. FEATURE EXTRACTION

This module was designed to extract the features from the segmented areas of the image containing the characters to be recognized, traits that serve to distinguish an area corresponding to a letter from an area corresponding to other letters. To begin with, the first n components of the discrete cosine transformation of a segmented area are considered to be the features that describe it. In the next phase, certain statistical details of the area are added to the discrete cosine transformation components to define its features.

6.5. TRAINING/TESTING NEURAL NETWORK

- It is mainly used for the purpose of machine learning i.e., we train the machine with a particular problem by giving it the inputs with the respective outputs.
- And once the machine is trained for such kind of input, and then we can use it as a solution to that problem.
- So the main task here is to train the machine and create the dataset for that.
- It mainly consists of two methods
- `ANN_TRAIN(String arg[])` – It is used for training of the svm and the path of the file with its name is passed as the parameter to it. It generates a model file which is used as reference to the trained dataset.
- `ANN_TEST(String arg[])` – It is used for the testing purpose and the path of model file, input file, output file is passed as the parameter to it. It writes the result of the input in the output file.

CHAPTER 7

ADAPTIVE THRESHOLDING

An important step in pre-processing an image for handwriting recognition is transforming it into black and white. Because such an image's histogram is bimodal, we can calculate a threshold that separates the handwriting from the background. One method which gives very good results in this case is developed by Nobuyuki Otsu (1979). Otsu's method is applied to images with gray levels and it considers that the pixels of the image are divided into two classes C_0 and C_1 separated by a threshold t . This method solves the problem of finding the optimum threshold t^* that minimises the error of classifying a background pixel as belonging to the foreground and vice versa (Cheriet *et al.*, 2007). Without loss of generalization, handwriting is defined as being the dark characters placed on light background. For an image with gray levels in $G = \{0, 1, \dots, L-1\}$, handwriting and the background can be represented by two classes as follows: $C = \{0, 1, \dots, t\}$ and $C = \{t+1, t+2, \dots, L-1\}$. The within class variance, between-class variance, and total-variance reach the maximum at equivalent threshold t . Using σ_W^2 , σ_B^2 and σ_T^2 to represent them, the Otsu method consists of an exhaustive search for the threshold which minimises the variance within a class, which is defined as a weighed sum of the variance of the two classes:

$$\sigma_W^2(t) = w_1(t)\sigma_1^2(t) + w_2(t)\sigma_2^2(t)$$

The w_i weights represent the probabilities of the two classes separated by a threshold t and σ_i the variance of these classes. Otsu shows that minimising the within-class variance is equivalent to maximising the between-class variance.

$$\sigma_B^2(t) = \sigma^2 - \sigma_W^2(t) = w_1(t)w_2(t)[\mu_1(t) - \mu_2(t)]^2$$

Where μ_i represents the mean value of class i .

The $w_1(t)$ probability is calculated based on the value of the t level from the histogram:

$w_1(t) = \sum_0^t p(i)$ and the class mean $\mu_1(t)$ is given by: $\mu_1(t) = \sum_0^t p(i)x(i)$ where $x(i)$ represents the i -th value of the histogram.

Similarly, we can calculate $w_2(t)$ and $\mu_2(t)$ for values that correspond to gray levels higher than t .

CHAPTER 8

SEGMENTATION

The solution for the segmentation of the areas of the characters in the image was given by an implementation of a new algorithm that, scanning the image from left to right and from bottom to top, and finding a black pixel, will consider it as the original area delimiting the character from which is part of. This area is further expanded in three directions, namely top, left and right, so as to include the rest of the pixels that are part of the handwritten character. Expansion in one direction is stopped when, among the new pixels brought by that expansion there's no black one. Expansion in that direction is resumed when the expansions in the other directions bring in its border new black pixels.

This process ends when either no more expansions in any direction can be done or when the algorithm finishes scanning the entire picture.

The steps of the algorithm are the following:

1-Scan the image from left to right and from bottom to top;

2-For each black pixel encountered which is not part of an area already found do:

2.1-Tag the up, left and right directions as possible expansions;

2.2-If there is a direction of which frontier contains no black pixels, mark this direction as not possible for expansion;

2.3-For all directions marked for expansion, increase the coordinates of the area in that direction coordinates with one unit

- 2.4-Repeat steps 2.2 - 2.3 as long as there is at least one direction marked for expansion;
- 2.5-Save the new area in a list and advance the current pixel coordinates over this one;
- 2.6- Resume algorithm from step 2.

CHAPTER 9

CHARACTER NORMALIZATION

Normalization (Cheriet *et al.*, 2007) is a process that results in regulating the size, position and shape of the segmented images of the characters so as to reduce the variation in size of the images belonging to the same class thus facilitating the extraction of features and increasing the accuracy of classification. Mainly there are two types of methods: linear and non-linear.

As presented in Fig. 8, we mark by W_1 and H_1 the width and height of the original character, and by W_2 and H_2 width and height of the normalized character and by L the size of the standard plane. This size is considered to be, usually, 32x32 or 64x64. We define the aspect ratios of the original character (R_1) and that of the normalized one (R_2) as:

$$R_1 = \frac{\min(W_1, H_1)}{\max(W_1, H_1)}$$

$$R_2 = \frac{\min(W_2, H_2)}{\max(W_2, H_2)}$$

which are always between [0,1].

Fig.9.1. The Original Character (1); The Normalized Character Which Fills The Standard Plane (2).

In the so-called “Aspect Ratio Adaptive Normalization” (ARAN), the aspect ratio of the normalized character R_2 is computed adaptively based on the original character R_1 . Using one of the functions in Table 8.1. In implementing this method, normalized character image is placed over a plan with flexible sizes (W_2, H_2) , then the plan is moved so that it is superimposed on the standard plan by aligning the centre. If the image fills one dimension of the normalized standard plane, then L is considered to be equal to $\max(W_2, H_2)$ and the other dimension is centred in the standard plane. With R_2 and L , we can calculate $\min(W_2, H_2)$ using the formula given above. Thus, we can obtain the size (W_2, H_2) of the normalized character.

Table 9.1
Functions For Aspect Ratio Mapping

Method	Function
Fixed aspect ration	$R_2 = 1$
Aspect ratio preserved	$R_2 = R_1$
Square root of aspect ratio	$R_2 = \sqrt{R_1}$
Cubic root of aspect ratio	$R_2 = \sqrt[3]{R_1}$
Sine of aspect ratio	$R_2 = \sqrt{\sin(\frac{\pi}{2} R_1)}$

Coordinate transformation from the original plan on the character in the normalized one is done using forward or backward mapping. If we denote the original image, respectively, the normalized one, by $f(x,y)$ and $g(x',y')$, the normalized image is

generated $g(x',y') = f(x,y)$ based on mapping coordinates. The forward and backward mappings are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} & x' = x'(x,y) \\ & y' = y'(x,y) \\ \text{and:} \\ & x = x(x',y') \\ & y = y(x',y') \end{aligned}$$

In case of the forward mapping, the x and y coordinates take discrete values, but $x'(x,y)$ and $y'(x,y)$ are not necessarily the same, while in the case of backward mapping the reverse is true. And furthermore, in the case of direct mapping the coordinates (x',y') do not necessarily occupy all the space in the normalized plane. Thusly, for using the normalization we need to implement mesh coordinates and pixel interpolation. By meshing, mapped coordinates (x',y') , (x,y) are approximated by the nearest integer $([x'],[y'])$ or $([x],[y])$.

In case of the mesh in the forward mapping, the discrete coordinates (x,y) scan the Original image pixels and the pixel value $f(x,y)$ are assigned to all the pixels that fall within the range $([x'(x,y)],[y'(x,y)])$ to $([x'(x+1,y+1)],[y'(x+1,y+1)])$.

The forward mapping is mostly used because of the fact that meshing the mapped coordinates (x,y) can be easily done.

The functions for the forward and backwards mapping are given in table. Denoted by α and β in the table, they are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &= W_2/W_1 \\ \beta &= H_2/H_1 \end{aligned}$$

Table 9.2
Functions For Coordinate Mapping

Method	Forward mapping	Backwards mapping
Linear	$x' = \alpha x$ $y' = \beta y$	$x = x'/\alpha$ $y = y'/\beta$
Moment	$x' = \alpha(x - x_c) + x'_c$ $y' = \beta(y - y_c) + y'_c$	$x' = \frac{(x' - x'_c)}{\alpha} + x_c$ $y' = \frac{(y' - y'_c)}{\beta} + y_c$
Non-linear	$x' = W_2 h_x(x)$ $y' = H_2 h_y(y)$	$x' = h_x^{-1}\left(\frac{x'}{W_2}\right)$ $y' = h_y^{-1}\left(\frac{y'}{H_2}\right)$

For extracting the features that define the characters in the image we used the discrete cosine transformation (Watson, 1994), which is a technique that converts a signal into its elementary frequency components. Each line of M pixels from an image can be represented as a sum of M weighted cosine functions, assessed in discrete points, as shown by the following equation (in the one-dimensional case):

$$T_i = \sum_{x=0}^{M-1} \frac{\sqrt{2}C_x}{\sqrt{M}} s_x \cos \frac{(2i+1)x\pi}{2M}$$

$$\text{for } 0 \leq i < M \text{ where } C_x = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \text{ for } x=0, \text{ otherwise } C_x = 1$$

In the bidimensional case, we consider a matrix \mathbf{S} of 8x8 elements defined by (Petrescu, 2006):

$$T_{i,j} = \frac{1}{4} C_i C_j \sum_{x=0}^7 \sum_{y=0}^7 s_{y,x} \cos \frac{(2x+1)j\pi}{16} \cos \frac{(2y+1)i\pi}{16}$$

In equation it is considered that $C_i = C_j = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$, for $i, j = 0$, otherwise $C_i = C_j = 1$.

It can be said that the transformed matrix elements with lower indices correspond to coarser details in the image and those with higher indices to finer details. Therefore, if we analyze the matrix \mathbf{T} obtained by processing different blocks of an image, we see that in the upper left corner of the matrix we have high values (positive or negative) and the more we explore down to the bottom right corner the values start to decline even more, tending to 0. The next step is the actual selection of certain elements in the array. The first operation that can be done is to order the elements of the matrix into a one dimensional array so as to highlight as many values of zero as possible. The ordering is done by reading the matrix in zigzag. To extract the necessary features for character recognition we can select the first N values from this array. As N increases, so does the recognition accuracy, but that happen at the expense of increasing the training time of the support vector machine.

CHAPTER 10

FEATURE EXTRACTION

This module was designed to extract the features from the segmented areas of the image containing the characters to be recognized, traits that serve to distinguish an area corresponding to a letter from an area corresponding to other letters. To begin with, the first n components of the discrete cosine transformation of a segmented area are considered to be the features that describe it. In the next phase, certain statistical details of the area are added to the discrete cosine transformation components to define its features:

- Number of black pixels from a matrix (the so called "on" pixels);
- mean of the horizontal positions of all the "on" pixels relative to the centre of the image and to its width;
- mean of the vertical positions of all the "on" pixels relative to the centre of the image and to its height;
- mean of horizontal distances between "on" pixels;
- mean of vertical distances between "on" pixels;
- mean product between vertical and horizontal distances of "on" pixels;
- mean product between the square of horizontal and vertical distances between all "on" pixels;

- mean product between the square of vertical and horizontal distances between all "on" pixels;
- mean number of margins met by scanning the image from left to right;
- Sum of vertical positions of the margins met by scanning the image from left to right;
- mean number of margins met by scanning the image from bottom to top;
- sum of horizontal positions of the margins met by scanning the image from top to bottom.

One last operation implemented by this module is the normalization of the results obtained up until now so as they correspond to the format accepted by the support vector machine module.

CHAPTER 11

TRAINING/TESTING NEURAL NETWORK

The module offers the possibility of selecting different types of kernel functions, such as the sigmoid, RBF, linear functions, and the setting of the various parameters of these kernels (Hsu *et al.*, 2010). After setting the type of kernel and its parameters, the support vector machine is trained with the set of features given by the other modules. Once the training is over, the support vector machine can be used to classify new sets of characters.

ANN mainly consists of two methods:-

ANN_TRAIN(String arg []) – It is used for training of the ann and the path of the file with its name is passed as the parameter to it. It generates a model file which is used as reference to the trained dataset.

ANN_TEST(String arg[]) – IT is used for the testing purpose and the path of model file, input file, output file is passed as the parameter to it. It writes the result of the input in the output file.

CHAPTER 12

LANGUAGE TRANSLATION

Translation is the communication of the meaning of a source-language text by means of an equivalent target-language text. The English language draws a terminological distinction (not all languages do) between translating (a written text) and interpreting (oral or sign-language communication between users of different languages); under this distinction, translation can begin only after the appearance of writing within a language community.

A translator always risks inadvertently introducing source-language words, grammar, or syntax into the target-language rendering. On the other hand, such "spill-overs" have sometimes imported useful source-language calques and loanwords that have enriched target languages. Translators, including early translators of sacred texts, have helped shape the very languages into which they have translated.

Translation is the communication of meaning from one language (the source) to another language (the target). Translation refers to written information, whereas interpretation refers to spoken information.

The purpose of translation is to convey the original tone and intent of a message, taking into account cultural and regional differences between source and target languages.

Translation has been used by humans for centuries, beginning after the appearance of written literature. Modern-day translators use sophisticated tools and technologies to accomplish their work, and rely heavily on software applications to simplify and streamline their tasks.

CHAPTER 13

SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS SPECIFICATION (SRS)

13.1 INTRODUCTION

This project, 'Handwritten Character Recognition' is a software algorithm project to recognize any handwritten text efficiently on android devices with image as an input which can either be a previously stored image from the gallery or provided through camera.

13.1.1 Purpose

The objective of this project is to identify handwritten characters with the use of neural networks. We have to construct suitable neural network and train it properly. The program should be able to extract the characters one by one and map the target output for training purpose. After automatic processing of the image, the training dataset has to be used to train "classification engine" for recognition purpose. The program code has to be written in JAVA and supported with the usage of Graphical User Interface (GUI) using android.

13.1.2 Scope

In this fast-paced world, there is an immense urge for the digitalization of printed documents and documentation of information directly in digital form. And there is still some gap in this area even today. OCR techniques and their continuous improvisation from time to time is trying to fill this gap. This project is about devising an algorithm for recognition of hand written characters also known as HCR (Handwritten Character Recognition) leaving aside types of OCR that deals with recognition of computer or typewriter printed characters.

Intended Audience and Reading Suggestions

This project is a functioning prototype for a handwritten text recognizer, and it is restricted within the college premises. This has been implemented under the guidance of college professors. This project is useful for the students, teachers as well as the business professionals who are trying to automate the handwritten to digital text conversion.

13.1.3 References

- <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org>
- <https://www.kaggle.in/datasets>
- <https://developer.android.com/docs>

13.1.4 Overview

The rest of the SRS examines the specifications of Handwritten Text Recognition and Translation. Section 2 of the SRS presents the overall description of the Handwritten Text Recognition and Translation. Section 3 outlines the detailed, specific functional, performance, system and other related requirements of the Handwritten Text Recognition and Translation.

13.2 OVERALL DESCRIPTION

To solve the defined handwritten character recognition problem of classification we used android user interface and python as a backend with Neural Network Toolbox and Image Processing. The computation code is divided into the next categories:

- Pre-processing of the image
- Feature extraction
- Creating an Artificial Neural Network
- Training & Testing of the network
- Recognition
- Language translator

13.2.1 Product Perspective

- **SOFTWARE:** It includes a software based on Android platform which is connected to the database of handwritten characters of more than hundreds of writers.
- **HARDWARE:** No hardware is involved.

13.2.2 Operating Environment

Operating environment for Handwritten Text Recognition and Translation is as listed below.

- Android enabled smartphone.
- An internet connected smartphone.

13.3 FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

13.3.1 Software Requirements

- An Android smartphone
- The proposed software installed along with all permissions granted.
- Minimum API 15
- Minimum Android version 4.0.3

13.3.2 Hardware Requirements

- NO HARDWARE REQUIRED

13.4 NON-FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

13.4.1 User Performance Requirements

The user's performance will be dependent on the speed of their Internet connection as well as the performance of the network. The project will be designed to be compatible

with all major Internet browsers and for a low common denominator of phone performance, so as to be widely accessible.

13.4.2 Other Non-Functional Attributes

13.4.2.1 Security

No security measures are expected to be involved excepting the web modification interface for maintenance, which will be protected.

13.4.2.2 Reliability

Based on up-time of server on which application resides. Regular backup of database, or backup server for application, may be required to ensure up-time and reliability.

13.4.2.3 Maintainability

A web-based database management engine will be developed for the maintenance of the database.

13.4.2.4 Portability

As a standards-driven web-based application, portability should not be an issue.

13.5 USE CASE DIAGRAM

The use case diagram representation of the project can be represented as shown in figure.

Use case diagram of the project basically involve-

1. User
2. Handwritten Optical Character Recognition
3. Deep Learning Algorithm
4. Translator
5. Dataset.

Fig 13.1: Use Case Diagram

PROJECT OVERVIEW

Fig 14.1: Splash Screen

Fig 14.2: Service Chooser Activity

Fig 14.3: Source Chooser Activity

Fig 14.4: Image Cropper Activity

Fig 14.5: Recognized Text

Fig 14.6 Translation Activity

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